

An Enquiry Concerning Artificial Intelligence through Social Networks

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Abstract

Despite problem-solving ability, the issues bothering artificial intelligence (AI) cause concern to the moral circuits. Questions such as what consequences machines make upon human nature and human nurture as social individuals in the community? What machines have become – servants or masters – in the face of upcoming civilization? AI supporters show optimism contrary to the non-supporters who question the credibility and safety of AI reality. The objective of the paper investigates the changes in the self and the social activities of users due to AI in the network society, Secondly, whether the AI technology modify moral standpoint of the people in the future. In synthesis, the way AI network resolves social problems of the society. The subject demands attention by gleaning the references for inquiry. The method of data collection drawn through the secondary sources by using meta-analysis technique from published journals from national and internal forums. AI represents knowledge, logic, and engineering by connecting pieces of facts to get a problem solved or a riddle answered in the real world as the proposition. The social network provides community and AI provide information to people. How by using AI the problems of the world resolved to protract debate and attention in the growth scenario, astutely.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Social network, Machines, Network society, AI Ethics

Introduction

Behind every pattern of digital communication, not only human intelligence but also artificial intelligence operates. Ever since the term artificial intelligence coined in 1955, programmers code machines to work and respond to user's preference. AI builds users community for social cohesion as much as user's dependence on AI for the automation tasks. The impact of AI on the user's community increases rapidly and affects the nature and the nurture of user's application. The subject enquires influence of AI on user's social and individual activities in the social network media. After the industrialization, the services of technology grew horizontally and vertically expanding corporations and communities by shaping the culture of society, especially, the part played by AI on the users' network, not only, affect knowledge about the real social world, but also, influencing the millennial population. In other words, AI reflects the network structure on the basis of users' database. The AI devices connected through portals not only create communication along the line but also network patterns. The social network, as a

type of artificial intelligence, communicates the social reality in the digital world. The intelligence of machines demonstrates the morphology of users. Therefore, AI as a unique communication system becomes a symbol of the social network society as in smart cars, surveillance, detecting fraud, fake news, customer service, video games, predictive purchasing, smart recommendation, smart homes, virtual assistants, preventing heart attack, identifying criminals, preserving wildlife, search and rescue, cyber security, work automation and maintenance prediction, hiring and firing and so on.

Artificial intelligence discloses social networks and functions with the web of partnerships as in Amazon, Google, Facebook, IBM, Microsoft, Apple, LinkedIn etc. Although, the ways in which devices serve man determines the quality of technology, even so the feedback loop of devices form network structure and allow interactions among and between users possible. The connected user-devices not only link network nodes but also onset communication of users along the line. If interactive media operates using pattern, then, the structural interaction of people in the web vindicate pattern as well. Moreover, the type of mind operates behind social interactions indeed produces knowledge about real connections of the social world. Similarly, artificial intelligence as a manmade system resolves problems programmatically. To sum up, the interface of AI serves community to build and transform public interest. Nevertheless, as a device, AI thinks and acts rationally like human beings to solve problems in network community. As science fictionist Vernor Vinge says, “I am suggesting that we recognize that in network and interface research there is something as profound (and potential wild) as Artificial Intelligence.”

Methodology

The paper argues AI as the digital framework for network society. In other words, the research investigates, how AI contribute to individual and social development of online community for users in network and ultimately to the individual and social construction of technological society. How technology bring changes through the means of AI with respect to the nature and nurture of individuals in society. In order to find out, research papers from journals and open sources written by field experts of secondary data sources were reviewed in the literature. Meta-analysis technique helped to review the sources from academic journals that analyze the findings of AI in digital society. “Artificial intelligence is here and being rapidly commercialized, with new applications being created not just for manufacturing but also for energy, healthcare, and oil and gas. This will change how we all do business”, says Joe Kaeser. The paper examines the social and individual improvement of users in the network society through ethical AI network technology.

Review of Literature

Framework of AI on individual and social network

Figure 1 AI on Individual and Social Network Pattern in Digital Platform

Note: AI-IN (Artificial Intelligence-Individual Network), ANN (Artificial Neural Network), PETs (Privacy Enhancing Technologies, DAI (Distributed Artificial Intelligence), AI- SN (Artificial Intelligence – Social Network), CN&SFG (Complex Networks and Scale Free Graphs), MAS (Multi Agent System), SMS (Social Media Software), SMA (Social Media Analytics), MN (Markov Network).

Stephen Hawking evaluating human and artificial intelligence states, “everything that civilization has to offer is a product of human intelligence... AI may provide... eradication of war, disease, and poverty would be high on anyone’s list. Success in creating AI would be the biggest event in human history (Hawking).” In this section, selective literature reviewed on AI under individual and social networks in relation to actions of users.

AI expand individual’s network (Nature): AI enhances nature of self, privacy, and influence of users. Artificial neural network, privacy enhancing technology (PETs), Ontograp of influential people may influence the nature of individuals in the network. AI-based privacy enhancing technologies (‘PETs) such as differential privacy and federal learning plus AI auditors and guardians may enhance security of individuals in the AI community (Els). AI influences on economic policy in terms of employment, inequality, and competition explains AI on individual and social networks (Agrawal, Gans and Goldfarb). The Emotion machines (Minsky) mimics the future plans of AI investment in creating feeling and emotions to serve man’s need. “Web mining in e-learning” provides with patterns for e-learner’s behavior and environment by login paths (Lappas). Similar works extend AI network for perception of individual’s nature of development.

AI expand social network (Nurture): The stories of web media support social inclusion arise out of social interaction. By using user-generated content and connecting intelligence, network science supplies knowledge about the social world. AI through network media shape users, corporations, and communities by impacting the millennial population.

AI functions as quality of technology in which devices mediate to serve people. For instance, distributed artificial intelligence stands as a platform to spread social knowledge and action. Complex networks and scale free graphs as a platform to spread social conventions.

Multi-agent system as a platform builds social trust and reputation to user’s interest. Social media software contributes in designing social intelligence. Social media analytics predict social media market for brand building. The study examines how technology derives social structure? Rather than how social structure derives technology to existing structure patterns? (Burkhardt and Brass).

The study conducted by Schmäzle, et al (Schmäzle, O’Donnell and Garcia) explains, “Social exclusion is associated with increased connectivity within the mentalizing system.” Distributed artificial intelligence as a platform to spread knowledge action; Grasser published on how knowledge and action spread using distributed artificial intelligence (DAI) through the open information systems semantics (Gasser).

The body of research that deals with intelligent communities that collaborate and coordinate knowledge-based processes contribute in social conception of knowledge and action to web community. Complex networks and scale free graphs as a platform to spread social conventions; Multi-agent system as a platform to explore users trust and reputation; Social media software designs contribute to social intelligence; Social media analytics predict market condition to build brands; Markov networks formulates complex real world scenario to study real social interactions.

Analysis of Review

AI versus Humans (morality): If the nature and nurture of users meet the parameters of following scale of ethics in producing AI network then such an action stands responsible one to the human community or else chances of deviation irresistible. AI actions within human network ethics framework derived from the normative ethics as in following table.

AI in Human Network Ethics

Moral Action Scale for Humans	AI extend individual's network (Nature)		AI extend social network (Nurture)	
	yes	no	yes	no
Virtuous	yes	no	yes	no
Rights respected	yes	no	yes	no
Dutiful	yes	no	yes	no
Rationality	yes	no	yes	no
Unbiased	yes	no	yes	no
Valuable	yes	no	yes	no
Happiness for many	yes	no	yes	no
State welfare	yes	no	yes	no
Good for the self	yes	no	yes	no
Loving results	yes	no	yes	no
Promotes knowledge	yes	no	yes	no
Economic welfare	yes	no	yes	no
Overall preference & satisfaction	yes	no	yes	no
interrelationship and interdependence	yes	no	yes	no
Reform based outcome, virtue,& duty	yes	no	yes	no

Source: derived from (Normative ethics)

AI as problem solver (social problems): The impacts of AI leads to “growth acceleration, human wage fall, and non-human value shaping the future” opine few (Christiano). AI in social network contribute, the level of social integration associated to aspects of individual health (Seeman). “Positive impact of AI promotes “international friendship and goodwill”, “articles cheaper”, “reduced the toil and sweat of the laborer”; Negative consequences results in, “materialistic life, inhuman qualities”, “disputes” “political hegemony”, “unemployment” and so on. (Paulo)

The literature on AI in social integration highlights the following social benefits;

- Distributed artificial intelligence as a platform to spread social knowledge and action:
- Complex networks and scale free graphs as a platform to spread social conventions:
- Multi-agent system as a platform to explore users social trust and reputation:
- Social media software designs contribute to social intelligence:
- Social media analytics predict social market condition to build brands:

“We argue that networks operate at the behavioral level through four primary pathways: (1) provision of social support; (2) social influence; (3) on social engagement and attachment; and (4) access to resources and material goods.” (Berkman, Glass and Brissette). Social network integrates people. A Study on elderly individuals provides understanding on how, “Poor social connections, infrequent participation in social activities, and social disengagement predict the risk of cognitive decline in elderly individuals” (Zunzunegui, Alvarado and Ser). The citations show uses of networked AI in communities. Therefore, AI cannot create the social problems in the networks unless ethics and morality sidelined or ignored in user faceoff situations.

Conclusion

“There is huge demand for artificial intelligence technologies”; “Facebook can be an accumulation of different intelligences” says Yuri Milner venture capitalist and physicist. The human morality examines AI in individual and social networks. According to the human ethics, AI actions weighed, gauged, evaluated and so derived. In the future, AI cannot be without ethics. In the phase of super intelligence, AI network influences individual (Nature) and social (Nurture) spheres of user community. In spite of all the limitations, “I believe this artificial intelligence is going to be our partner. If we misuse it, it will be a risk. If we use it right, it can be our partner.” Masayoshi Son. To sum, the enquiry of AI begins with network effect and ends with human morality show accountability of the technological inventions and innovations rather than mere delusion or AI apocalypse for upcoming ages of human civilization.

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